

Phytochemical, Proximate Analysis and Mineral Composition of Aqueous Crude Extract of *Ficus Asperifolia* Miq.

Ojo O.A^{1*}, Ajiboye B.O¹, Ojo A.B², Onikanni S.A¹, Olarewaju O.I²

1. Department of Chemical Sciences, Biochemistry Unit, Afe Babalola University.
2. Department of Biochemistry, Ekiti State University.

*Corresponding author: Ojo O.A

Department of Chemical Sciences, Biochemistry Unit,
Afe Babalola University, Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria.
Phone: +07037824647
E-mail: boluwafemiadeleke08@gmail.com

Received: January 15, 2014, Accepted: February 8, 2014, Published: February 10, 2014.

ABSTRACT

To determine the chemical constituents, proximate, phytochemical analysis and mineral composition of the crude aqueous extract of the leaves of *Ficus asperifolia*. The extracts were subjected to proximate and phytochemical screening. The mineral contents were determined using standard biochemical methods and equipment. Phytochemical studies carried out on aqueous extract of *Ficus asperifolia* leaves showed the presence of alkaloid, saponin, phenol, tannin, cardiac glycoside, steroid, cardenolides and phlobatannins while terpenes, flavonoids, anthraquinones and chalcones were not detected. Analyses showed that the sample has high level of Carbohydrate (42.64%), moderate amount of Crude Fibre and Protein (18.41 and 14.73%), respectively and little amount of Ash content (9.78%) and Crude Fat (3.16%). Also a considerable level (11.29%) of moisture was shown. This composition shows that the sample could be a good source of Carbohydrate, Dietary Fibre and Protein. Sodium and Potassium content (0.185 ± 0.002 and $0.367 \pm 0.007\%$), respectively indicates the tendency of *Ficus asperifolia* to be able to regulate or control the osmotic balance of the body fluid as well as body pH. *Ficus asperifolia* is also found to be rich in Phosphorus ($0.349 \pm 0.002\%$) and Calcium ($0.203 \pm 0.002\%$), which is essential for bone formation. Magnesium, ($0.428 \pm 0.003\%$) is also present, which could help to lower the blood pressure. Antioxidant minerals Zinc (64.45 ± 0.15 mg/kg), Iron (7.00 ± 0.20 mg/kg), Copper (13.35 ± 0.15 mg/kg) and Selenium (0.0027 ± 0.01 mg/kg) are also present. Our findings therefore, suggest that there is an indication that *Ficus asperifolia* contains important phytochemicals, proximate and mineral compounds that may be linked to its beneficial effects on health.

Keyword: Phytochemical, Mineral composition, proximate, Aqueous extract, *Ficus asperifolia*,

INTRODUCTION

Medicinal leaves are significant sources of synthetic and herbal medications. In most rural and urban areas of sub-Saharan Africa such as in Southern-Nigeria, medicinal herbs are used as raw drugs, extracts and/or tinctures [1]. The past few decades have witnessed rapid progress in the use of leaf phytochemical and herbal products as popular and alternative treatment remedies [2, 3, 4]. The active ingredients of leaves that can provide effective therapeutic potential can occur in all leaf structures but concentration is often higher in one part, such part is preferred. Examples include roots, flower, fruit, leaves and seeds [5]. Phytochemicals may be described as non-nutritive leaf chemicals that have protective or disease preventive properties. They are regarded as non-essential nutrients [6]. They are naturally occurring bioactive molecules produced by leaf for protection

from the elements of the earth and the sun's harmful rays. These amazing phyto-compounds provide food resources for the human cells. Consumption of leaf foods containing these compounds have been scientifically validated to help slowdown the aging process and reduce the risk factors of many diseases including cancer, heart disease, stroke, high blood pressure, cataracts, osteoporosis, diabetes and urinary tract infections [7, 8, 9]. Biologically, active compounds from natural sources have always been of great interest to scientists working on infectious diseases. In recent years there has been growing interest to evaluate leaves possessing antibacterial activity for various diseases [10]. A number of studies have been reported, dealing with antimicrobial screening of extracts of medicinal leaves [10, 11, 12]. Today, it is estimated that leaf materials are present in, or have provided the

model for 50% western drugs [1]. Many commercially proven drugs used in modern medicine were initially used in crude form in traditional or folk healing practices, or for other purposes that suggested potentially useful biological activity. *Ficus asperifolia* belonging to the Moraceae family is a small or average size tree, terrestrial or epiphyte which can reach 20 m in height. It is found in Nigeria, Senegal, Uganda, Tanzania, Natal (South Africa), Madagascar and Cameroon. *Ficus asperifolia* is abundant in the savannah regions, especially along river banks and marshy areas at an altitude of up to 1100 m. The leaves are enormous and displayed spirally, the limb is largely oval or has a form of ellipse and the roots are most often fibrous [13]. In many traditional medicines of Africa, the leaf extract of *F. asperifolia* is used as an anthelmintic and a purgative [14]. This study intends to determine the chemical constituents, proximate, phytochemical analysis and mineral composition of the crude aqueous extract of *Ficus asperifolia* Miq.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of leaf material and Preparation of leaf extract

Fresh samples of the leaves without stalk were collected from the local population in Ado town, Ekiti state, Nigeria. The leaf was identified and authenticated at the Department of Plant Sciences, Ekiti State University, Nigeria. The aqueous extract of the powdered *Ficus asperifolia* Miq. was air-dried in the laboratory at ambient temperature ($30 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) for 10 days, pulverized using a laboratory mechanical grinder (Christy and Norris limited, machine type 8) and the fine powders obtained stored until further use. 50g of the powdered sample was extracted with distilled water of 500ml for 48hrs. The mixture was decanted and filtered using sterile whatman paper No1. The filtrate measured up to 425ml and evaporated to dryness using a freeze dryer to obtain 12 % yield. The crude extract was later subjected to bioassay analyses. From the stock solution, concentration 10mg/ml was obtained by serial dilution. These were stored at 15°C until further use.

Phytochemical Analyses

Phytochemical analyses; tannin, alkaloid, saponin, steroid, phenol, phlobatannin, terpenoid, flavonoids, anthraquinones, chalcones, cardenolides and cardiac glycoside were determined using standard procedures [15, 16, 17].

Proximate Analyses

The parameters determined for proximate analyses include ash, moisture, crude protein, fat, fiber and carbohydrate. All of these were carried out using the method of analyses described by [18].

Mineral Analyses

The atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS) was used for the analyses of the following metals: Mg, Zn, Fe, Co, Cu, Se, Al, Ca and P while the Flame Photometer was used in the analyses of K & Na. Using AAS, a known amount of the sample was placed in a dish and heated with burnsen burner in a fume cupboard until there was no smoke emitted. This was transferred to the dessicator in other for it to cool after which 0.1m HCl solution was added to the ash. The resulting solution was filtered and diluted. Suitable

salts of the metals in questions were used to make their standards, lamps were fixed and the analyses were done. Using the flame photometer, the diluents of sample was aspirated into the jenway Digital flame photometer using the filter corresponding to each mineral element. All of these were carried out using the method of analyses described by [19].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of proximate analyses are shown in table 1.

Parameter	(%)
Crude Protein	14.73
Crude Fibre	18.41
Crude Fat	3.16
Ash	9.78
Moisture	11.29
Carbohydrate	42.64

Table 2 Phytochemical Screening of Leaf Extracts of *Ficus asperifolia*.

Phytochemical	Extract Content
Alkaloids	+++
Tannin	+
Phlobatannins	+
Saponin	+++
Flavonoids	-
Anthraquinones	-
Steroids	+
Terpenes	-
Cardenolides	+
Phenol	+++
Chalcones	-
Cardiac Glycosides	++

+ = Trace amount ++ = Moderate amount, +++ = Appreciable amount - = Completely Absent

Phytochemical analyses conducted on the *Ficus asperifolia* leaf extracts revealed the presence of constituents which are known to exhibit medicinal as well as physiological activities similar to the study done by [20]. Analyses of the leaf extracts revealed the presence of phytochemicals such as phenols, tannins, steroids, saponins, glycosides, alkaloids, phylobatannins and cardenolides (table 2). However, flavonoids, anthraquinones, terpenes and chalcones are absent. The leaf extracts to produce inhibitory effect on inflammation [21]. Saponins have the property of precipitating and coagulating red blood cells. Some of the characteristics of saponins include formation of foams in aqueous solutions, hemolytic activity, cholesterol binding properties and bitterness [22]. Steroids have been reported to have antibacterial properties, [23, 24] and they are very important compounds especially due to their relationship with compounds such as sex hormones [25]. Alkaloids have been associated with medicinal uses for centuries and one of their common biological properties is their cytotoxicity [26]. Several workers have reported the analgesic [27], antispasmodic and antibacterial properties of alkaloids. Glycosides are known to lower the blood pressure according to many reports [28]. The results obtained in this study thus suggest the identified phytochemical compounds may be the bioactive constituents and this leaf is proving to be an increasingly valuable reservoir of bioactive compounds of substantial medicinal merit. The results of mineral analysis are shown in table 3.

Table 3 Mineral Composition of *Ficus asperifolia*

Element	Concentration
Sodium (Na)	0.185±0.002 %
Potassium (K)	0.367±0.007 %
Calcium (Ca)	0.203±0.002 %
Magnesium (Mg)	0.428±0.003 %
Phosphorus (P)	0.349±0.002 %
Zinc (Zn)	64.45±0.150 mg/kg
Copper (Cu)	13.35±0.150 mg/kg
Iron (Fe)	7.00±0.200 mg/kg
Cobalt (Co)	3.55±0.150 mg/kg
Aluminum (Al)	0.485±0.250 mg/kg
Selenium (Se)	0.0027±0.010 mg/kg

The average carbohydrate content (42.64%), which is the highest parameter, will be a good source of Carbohydrate. Carbohydrates provide readily accessible fuel for physical performance and regulate nerve tissue [29]. Average crude fibre (18.41%) was the second highest parameter noted and this implies that they can serve as a source of dietary fibre [30] and can be employed in the treatment of diabetes, obesity and gastrointestinal tract diseases. It is also an indication that it contains a proportion of Cellulose, Hemicellulose and Lignin [31]. Average moisture content (11.29%) was the fourth highest Parameter noted. Too much of moisture in any sample has been proved to cause caking especially in flour and can also determine the Storage or shelf life and the viability of microorganisms' growth [32]. The lowest parameter noted was average crude fat content (3.16%), which are universally stored forms of energy in living organisms. They are major structural elements of biological membranes as phospholipids and sterols [33]. Average ash content (9.78%) is a reflection of the mineral contents preserved in the leaves. Minerals are essential for the proper functioning of tissues and act as second messengers in some biochemical cascade mechanisms [34]. Average crude protein (14.73%), would serve as enzymatic catalyst, mediate cell responses, control growth and cell differentiation [29]. The elemental analysis revealed the presence of phosphorus, magnesium, calcium and sodium in appreciable quantities. This precludes that the leaf could be a good source of nutrition for body building and a booster to immune system. Phosphorus has been reported to be good for bones and teeth formation. It contributes to energy production by participating in the breakdown of carbohydrates, protein and fats. It is needed for growth, maintenance and repair of tissues and cells and for the production of DNA and RNA [35]. Phosphorus is also needed to balance, and metabolize vitamins and minerals such as vitamin D, Calcium, Iodine, Magnesium and Zinc. Magnesium is an essential mineral involved in various metabolic reactions [36]. The presence of calcium explains why the leaf is important in blood clotting, muscle contraction and in the metabolic processes of certain enzymes. The concentration of iron is also of significance in the leaf. Most studies indicated that iron deficiency leads not only to behavioral changes but also to biochemical changes in the brain [37]. Iron plays a pivotal role in erythropoiesis and in many intracellular reactions of oxygen transport. It facilitates the oxidation of carbohydrate, proteins and fats. Calcium in conjunction with phosphorus and magnesium are activator of many enzyme systems and maintains the electrical potential in the nerves [37, 38]. Phosphorus assists calcium in many body reactions although it also has independent functions. Sodium and potassium are required to maintain osmotic balance of the body

fluids, pH of the body, regulate muscle and nerve irritability and control of glucose absorption [39].

CONCLUSION

From the research, it has been established through the proximate screening that *Ficus asperifolia* can be used as a good source of carbohydrate and protein. Also, a good source of minerals plays important roles in metabolic activities in the body. The results further revealed the presence of medicinally important constituents in the leaf *Ficus asperifolia*, and several studies carried out by numerous authors are supportive of this view. The traditional medicine practice is recommended strongly for these leaf as well as it is suggested that further work should be carried out to isolate, purify, and characterize the active constituents responsible for the activity of these leaves. Also additional work is encouraged to elucidate the possible mechanism of action of new constituents in the extract.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The Authors wish to acknowledge Mr. Omotayo of the Department of plant Science, Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria in helping to identify the plant and the Afe Babalola University biochemistry Laboratory where the research is conducted.

REFERENCES:

1. TMP. Traditional Medicine Policy for Nigeria. 2006; 6-66.
2. Hostettmann K, Marston A. Chemistry and Pharmacology of Natural Products: Saponins. Cambridge University Press, Uk. 1998;326-327.
3. Pattanayak SP, Mazumder PM. Effect of *Dendrophthoe falcata* (L.f.) Ettingsh on female reproductive system in Wistar rats: a focus on antifertility efficacy. *Contraception*. 2009; 80(3):314-320.
4. Jaouad Bouayed J, Piri K, Rammal H, Dicko A, Desor F, Younos F, Soulimani R. Comparative evaluation of the antioxidant potential of some Iranian medicinal leaves. *Food Chem*. 2007;104(1):364-368.
5. Akinleye OB Adu OE and Ayeni IA: Studies of some biological and chemical characteristics of Mexican sunflower (*Tithonia diversifolia*) *Consultation Research Journal* 1 (1), page 35 – 38. 1996.
6. Okwu DE, Okwu ME. Chemical composition of spondia mombin leaves. *J Sustain Agric Env*. 2004;6:140-147.
7. Liu RA. Potential synergy of phytochemicals in cancer prevention: mechanism of action. *J Nutr*. 2004;134(12 suppl):3479s-3485s.
8. Roa AV, Rao LG. Carotenoids and human health. *Pharmacol Res*. 2007;55(3):207-16.
9. Barjesteh van Waalwijk van Doorn-khosrovani S, Janssen J, Maas IM, Godschalk RW, Nijhuis JG, van Schooten FJ. Dietary flavonoids induce MLL translocations in primary human CD34+ cells. *Carcinogenesis*. 2007;28(8):1703-9.
10. Dhir ML Crayg G and Berman FW: Screening of Indian Leaves for biological activity. *India J. Exptal Biol*. 6:237-247. 2002
11. Adodo A: Nature power - a Christian approach to herbal medicine. Page 288. 2004
12. Idu M: The antibiotic properties of some Africa herbs. The nerbal Doctor. *A journal of African Medicine* Vol. 1 No. 2: 7-8. 2007
13. Adjanohoun JC, Aboubaker N, Dramane K, Ebot ME, Ekpere JA, Enow-Orock EG: *Contribution to Ethnobotanical and*

- Floristic Studies in Cameroon*. Lagos, Nigeria: OUA/STRC; Traditional medicine and pharmacopoeia; pp. 301–325. 1996
14. Soforowa A. *Leafes Médicinales et Médecine Traditionnelle d'Afrique*. Paris, France: Edition Karthala; 1996.
 15. Sofowora A: *Medicinal Leafs and Traditional Medicines in Africa*. Chichester John Willey & Sons New York;1993:256.
 16. Trease G.E, Evans W.C: *A Text-book of Pharmacognosy*. Bailliere Tindall Ltd, London; 1989:53
 17. Harborne J.B: *Phytochemical Methods: A Guide to Modern Techniques of Leaf Analysis*. Chapman A &Hall.London; :279, 1973.
 18. Onyeike EN. and Osuji JO. *Research Techniques in Biological and Chemical Sciences*. Springfield Publishers Ltd., Owerri, Nigeria. pp: 403, 2003.
 19. Oshodi AA. Proximate Consumption, Nutritionally valuable Minerals and Functional properties of *Adenopus breviflorus* benth seed and Protein concentrate. *Food Chem*. 1992; 45: 79- 83.
 20. Aiyegororo OA, Okoh AI. Preliminary phytochemical screening and in vitro antioxidant activities of aqueous extract of *Helichrysum longifolium* DC. *BMC compl. And Alt. Med*. 2001;10:21.
 21. Just MJ, Recio MC, Giner RM, Cueller MU, Manez S, Billia AR, Rios JL. Antiinflammatory activity of unusual lupine saponins from *Bupleurum fruticosens*. 1998;64:404-407.
 22. Sodipo OA, Akiniyi JA, Ogunbamosu JU. Studies on certain on certain characteristics of extracts of bark of *Pansinystalia macruceras* (K schemp) picrre Exbeille. *Global J. Pure Appl. Sci*. 2000;6:83-87.
 23. Cowan MM. Leaf products as antimicrobial agents. *Clin. Microbiol. Rev*. 1999;564-582.
 24. Okwu DE. Evaluation of chemical composition of medicinal leafs belonging to Euphorbiaceae. *Pak Vet. J*. 2001; 14:160-162.
 25. Nobori T, Miurak K, Wu DJ, Takabayashik LA, Carson DA. Deletion of cyclindependent kinase-4 inhibitor gene in multiple human cancers. *Nature*. 1994; 46:753-756.
 26. Antherden LM. *Textbook of Pharmaceutical Chemistry*, 8edn, Oxford University Press, London. 1969; 813-814.
 27. Okwu DE, Okwu ME. Chemical composition of *Spondias mombin* linn. Leaf parts. *J. Sustain. Agric. Environ*. 2004;6(2):140-147.
 28. Nyarko AA, Addy ME. Effects of aqueous extract of *Adenia cissampeloides* on blood pressure and serum analyte of hypertensive patients. *Phytotherapy Res*. 1990; 4(1):25- 28.
 29. Whitney EN and Rolfes SR. *Understanding Nutrition*. 10th Edn., Thomson/Wadsworth Publishing Company, Belmont, CA., pp: 132-137; 2005.
 30. Adeyeye EI and Ayejuyo OO. Chemical composition of *Cola Gluminate* and *Garcinia kola* seeds grown in Nigeria. *J. Food Sci.*, 2000; 45: 223-230.
 31. Agostoni CB, Carratu C, Boniglia E, Riva and Sanzini E. Free amino acid content in standard infant formulas: Comparison with human milk. *J. Am. College Nutr.*, 2001; 19: 434-438.
 32. Saldanha LG. Fibre in Diet of U.S Children: Results of National Survey. *Pediatrics*, 2003; 96: 994-996.
 33. Nelson DL and Cox MM. *Lehninger Principles of Biochemistry*. 5th Edn., W.H. Freeman and Company. Madison Avenue, New York, pp: 343; 2008.
 34. Antia BS, Akpan EJ, Okon PA and Umoren IU. Nutritive and anti-nutritive evaluation of sweet potatoes (*Ipomoea batatas*) leaves. *Pak. J. Nut.*, 2006; 5: 166-168.
 35. Pamplona – Roger GD:. *Encyclopedia of medicinal leafs*. Education and Health library, Vol 2. Editorial safeliz, S.I Spain. 2000
 36. Nishiura J Campus A Boim M and Schor N. Effect of *Phyllanthus niruri* on urinary calcium levels in calcium stone formingpatients. *Journal of Clinical and Laboratory Investigation of Urolothes and Related Areas* 32 2005 (15):362-366.
 37. de Oliverira AC Perez AC Merino G Prieto JG and Alvarez AI. Protective effects of *Panax ginseng* on muscle injury and inflammation after eccentric exercise. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology* 2001 130c: 369-377.
 38. Freitas AM Schor N and Boim MA. The effect of *Phyllanthus niruri* on urinary inhibitor of calcium oxalate Crystallization and other factors associated with renal stone formation *BJU int*. 2002; 89 (9): 829-834.
 39. Nwanjo HU. Studies on the effect of aqueous extract of *Phyllanthus niruri* leaf on plasma glucose level and some hepatospecific marker in diabetic Wistar rats. *The Internet Journal of Laboratory Medicine* 2007; 2 (2):55-62.

Citation: Ojo O.A(2014) Phytochemical, Proximate Analysis and Mineral Composition of Aqueous Crude Extract of *Ficus Asperifolia* Miq. *J. Advancement in Medical and Life Sciences*. V1-I1.

Copyright: © 2014 Ojo O.A, et al. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.